

Reality distortion and its effect on selected Hollywood herculean films

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Abstract

This article examined the extent of reality distortion in Hollywood Herculean contents, to critically analyse how these contents contribute to reality. The specific objectives of the article are to establish the intertextuality of the selected Hollywood films, to critically ascertain the extent of reality distorted by the elements employed and to determine the impact of such distortions on the content of the selected films. To achieve these, relevant concepts and empirical studies have been reviewed and the Reflective Projective Theory is adopted to establish a workable theoretical framework. The article employs discourse analysis as a methodology with emphasis on the critical discourse approach and three films in the Hollywood herculean genre are purposively selected. The selected Hollywood films (the *Thunder Force*, *Wonder Woman* and *Project Power*) are synoptically discussed and the rhetorical tropes and modalities employed in the elaboration of the storylines are also critically analysed. The suggestions embedded in the films are paradigmatically evaluated and the article advocates that to achieve absolute communication and believability, realism distorted actions in film can be replaced with actions that match actual reality in order to address arising societal issues today.

Key Words: Reality Distortion, Screen-Reality, Hollywood, Herculean, Films

Introduction

The ideas and emotions communicated in films would not be logical if the concepts of realism and reality are not well articulated and connected to bring about visual appreciation. Realism has a way of making something seem real and suggests that reality has an absolute existence that is independent of our thoughts, ideas and even consciousness. Inyang (2017) reasons that even though films are largely fictions and seek mainly to entertain viewers, there needs to be a strong connection between what happens in the mediated world and the real world, otherwise there would be a dissonance between what is supposed to be and what is in the movie world and the viewers would experience mental discomfort. Severny (2013) views film as an exertion of graphic art that simulates experiences which connect ideas, feelings, perceptions, stories, atmosphere or beauty, with the use of moving images. Films are made of sound and moving pictures recorded for cinema and television, they tell stories and represent real life situations. Film can serve as a means of recreation, as well as a potent medium

for education and proselytization. Realism in film can be considered as 'an equal slice of life' that is left at the interpretative discretion of the viewers who decode the content of the film based on individual prejudices. It can also be seen as 'reality on screen'. Realism is the reproduction of reality that can be achieved in the absence of exaggeration, deceit and tricks. Reality tends to be distorted when certain elements used in the narrative do not connect or relate to real life situations. The employment of visual elements and codes that ignore the reflection of reality often misrepresent reality and those that do not portray the viewers' immediacy and possibilities are often concluded on the bases of myths and deceptions thereby defeating the essence of filming. Such content may provoke laughter but do not in any way result in a sustainable imprint on the viewers' minds when realities are not portrayed.

Hollywood has overtime, been a leading film industry in the global scene. In order words, Hollywood can be considered as the model industry on the dashboard of global film. Other

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newer and emerging industries most often adopt a level of pattern and standards portrayed by Hollywood, even though such adoptions may be subjected to cultural infringement, shallow exposure and technological bereavement. In Africa especially in Nigeria, the average man on the street perceives any foreign movie that is not Chinese or Indian as American. To them, American films are the standard for movies worth their salt. With this, Hollywood has sold America to the world, so America is now seen as a model society without fault. Contributing to this claim are the computer-generated images, mise-en-scene, obsolescence and technologies employed in the Hollywood action narratives which form a misconceived America in the minds of a common African viewer.

Additionally, the high demand and preference for Hollywood action contents by an average African point to a bid to escape from actual reality. With the upsurge of insurgency, economic meltdown and political tussles that birth unemployment and poverty among other effects in the Sub-Saharan Africa especially, people try to escape from this reality by seeking and opting for motion contents that deviate from the level of realism that portrays actual reality. Anything that keeps reminding a man of his problem adds to the problem, especially when the resources for the resolution are unreachable but anything that tries to make a man forget his problem eases the mind. People tends to go for contents that ease their minds even when reality is distorted at this expense. This assertion tends to justify the preference for Hollywood herculean contents which present scenes with tower jumps, flying automobiles, vanishing humans and spectrals, monster/vampire fights, sun travels, among others. Such scenes which employ computer generated images may be misconceived to be real while also being referred to as film tricks by an average African Hollywood viewer.

The Concept of Realism

Realism is the appearance of reality, it attempts to present things in their true nature, and to deal with them as they are. In the arts generally, realism attempt to represent a subject matter truly, devoid of artificiality, speculative fiction and paranormal elements. The term 'realism' has been used side-by-side with 'naturalism', even though the terms are not synonymous. Naturalism has to do with visual representation in art that strives to represent objects with the least possible amount of distortion (Dillon & Raffel, 2021). Realism is predicated on a true-to-life representation and is a departure from the idealism of earlier scholastic

art, it refers to a historical movement of art that was originated in France after the French Revolution of 1848.

Realism has a way of making something seem real; it deals with the fact that reality has an absolute existence that is independent from our thoughts, ideas and even consciousness. The conventions of realistic fiction were established by early forms of the novel, although they were preceded by realism in the arts (McQuail, 2010). Realistic fiction depends on a certain attitude that what is portrayed is 'true to life', if not literary true in the sense of having occurred. Realism in film stems from the belief that it could occur or might have done so. Fantastic storylines can be given life by using the actual setting and social backgrounds and gaining verisimilitude –the appearance of reality, by applying plausible logics of action.

Realism is indeed a multifarious concept. Hall (2003)'s research on exploration of audience evaluations suggests that plausibility, perceptual persuasiveness, factuality, typicality, emotional involvement and narrative consistency are different dimensions of exploring realism. She concludes that different genres require different concepts of realism.

McQuail (2010) further posits that there are techniques of writing and filming that emphasize realism. According to him, in writing, accurate documentary-like descriptions and concrete, logical and sequential storytelling achieve this result. In filming, aside from representing real places, a continuous flow of action serves to create a realistic illusion. Sometimes black and white film stock is inserted (for instance, in flashbacks) to indicate that films have a real or documentary character. There are also classic realistic stylistic devices (Monaco, 1981). One of these is the 'shot, reverse shot', which moves the camera from one speaker to a partner in a dialogue to create the illusion for the spectator of involvement in the on-going conversation (Fiske, 1987).

Film can also employ the documentary mode or style, which is established on the basis of learned conventions. Documentary style relies on real places and social setting to create the illusion of actuality. According to Fiske (1987), media realism leads in a 'reactionary' (rather than a radical) direction because it 'naturalizes' the status quo –making it seem normal and therefore inevitable. In the terms used above, realism goes in the direction of 'closure', since the more real the portrayal seems, the more difficult it is for the reader, who is likely to take the reality of the world for granted, to establish any alternative

meanings. This relates back to Schlesinger *et al.*'s (1983) evidence about differing degrees of openness and closure in news and fiction.

Fiske (1987) for example, gives an example based on the television police series 'Cagney and Lacey', which features two women as chief protagonists. In the series, 'the discourse of gender ...underwrites a number of codes to discourage us from adopting the masculine point of view that it is normal in patriarchal television'. The female active role is 'represented as domineering, lively person that the camera dwells on, not just to show her sexual appeal, but to open up and express the manner in which she is manipulating the scene' (Fiske 1987, p53). Several factors tend to establish realism in film: shots are inclined to be objective, viewers view the *mise-en-scène* without the camera controlling their perception, editing is inclined to be seamless underscoring continuity, the camera inclines to be at eye level, composition seems random or natural, with an open frame, lighting appears to be natural, neither high contrast or washed out, real locations tend to be used instead of sets, music and theme songs tend to be diegetic.

Hollywood: The American Film Industry

Hollywood is a part of the United States film industry that is located in Los Angeles, California and has a reputation for making very successful films. It had over time become synonymous with the entire American film industry as it birthed many notable studios like Columbia Pictures, Disney, Paramount Pictures, Warner Bros. and Universal Pictures. Apart from being the name of a city, Hollywood has become one of the world's universal testimonials and a collective symbol of determination, accomplishment and attraction. Many of the famous film industries in the world derived their appellations from Hollywood and perceive it as a model film industry.

Hale (2015) traces the history of the Hollywood films to the late end of the 19th century. He however noted that the origin of films and motion pictures started in the late 1800's, with the discovery of moving toys devised to trick the eye to see an illusion of movement from an exhibition of static frames in quick succession like the thaumatrope and the zoetrope. Edward Muybridge in 1872 created the first film made by arranging some cameras on a speedway and preparing them to capture shots in quick succession while a horse passed in front of their lenses.

The first 'film for motion photography' according to Hale (2015) was invented by George Eastman and William Walker in 1885, and this

aided the development of motion photography. The Lumiere brothers (Auguste and Louis) then invented the cinematographe, to pick up pictures and to project still frames in quick progression. Hale (2015) added that the 1900's saw a great advancement of film and motion picture. Journeying into editing, settings, and visual flow encouraged ambitious filmmakers to drive into a new creative territory. One of the earliest movies produced during this period was *The Great Train Robbery* by Edwin Porter in 1903.

In 1910, director D.W. Griffith was sent the west coast with his acting troop to film on an empty lot in Los Angeles. The American Mutoscope and Biograph Company decided thereon to break new grounds. They traveled several miles north to a little friendly village and started filming there. This place was called Hollywood. In 1910, Griffith filmed the first ever movie in Hollywood titled: *In Old California*, a melodrama of California in the 1800s, as it was still part of Mexico then. Biograph stayed back some months and produced many films before going back to New York. When this wonderful place became popular in 1913, many movie-makers move towards the west to circumvent the fees imposed by Thomas Edison - the owner of the patents on the movie-making process. The studios and Hollywood grew together in Los Angeles before the World War I and made several movies in U.S. cities. Filmmakers then moved to southern California as the industry grew. Filmmakers were fascinated by the moderate ambience and consistent daylight that gave room for the filming of outdoor movies all year round with diverse vista. Numerous start out points for American cinema can be advanced, but it was Griffith's *Birth of a Nation* that launched the filmic lexicon that stands out celluloid up till today.

Nickelodeon also proffered an easygoing and economical way for the masses to watch movies. Nickelodeons helped the film industry to move into the 1920's by swelling the shared fascination of movies and to create additional income for filmmakers, together with the extensive use of theaters to screen the World War I propaganda. The end of the World War I steered the United States into a cultural explosion, as a new business was on the rise: Hollywood, the home of motion pictures in America. Hale (2015) notes that by 1919, Hollywood had transformed into the face of American cinema and all the glamour it would come to embody.

The American film industry truly began to flourish in the 1920s when hundreds of movies were being produced yearly. At that time

Hollywood rose to become an American force. Hollywood was regarded as a cultural icon set apart from the rest of Los Angeles, symbolizing leisureliness, extravagance, and a growing event panorama. This age also witnessed the rise of two coveted roles in the movie industry: the director and the star (Hale, 2015). Many cinematic works came to light during this period of highly controlled filmmaking, reason being that with the many movies produced, not every Tom, Dick and Harry had to be a big hit. A studio was able to play with a small-budget feature with a good script and fairly unfamiliar casts: *Citizen Kane*, directed by Orson Welles (1915-1985) which is widely professed as one of the greatest movies of all time, is in that class. Some other resolute directors like Howard Hawks (1896-1977) and Frank Capra (1897-1991) fought to exhibit their creative ideas. The peak of the studio system may have been the year 1939, which saw the release of such classics as *The Wizard of Oz*, *Gone with the Wind*, *Stagecoach*, *Mr. Smith Goes to Washington*, *Only Angels Have Wings*, *Ninotchka*, and *Midnight*. Among the other films in the Golden Age period that remain classics to the present day: *Casablanca*, *It's a Wonderful Life*, the original *King Kong*, and *Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs*.

Theoretical Framework

This article is built around the Reflective Projective Theory. Society keeps evolving and changing. The thoughts, mind-sets, and ideas of cultures world over are also changing due to the influences that people perceive. Mass media like film act like a mirror to society –they reflect society's attitudes and values while simultaneously proffering a vision of what society should look like. Media play pivotal roles in liberating and uniting people as well as societies. For instance, when one goes on social media to watch television, listen to radio or read printed materials at home, he/she is informed about what is going on globally. While sitting in our rooms, we can roam around the world because the media allow us to interact with the society, they allow us to feel the happenings, occurrences and events of the entire world from our comfort zone.

The society we live in has been in existence for a very long time. According to Wells *et al* (2011, p.72), “critics of advertising tend to believe that advertising has the power to shape social trends and the way that people think, while advertising professionals tend to believe that the best, they can do is spot trends and develop advertising messages that connect with them. They believe that advertising mirrors values rather

than sets them”. So, it is for every other form or activity of the mass media. While critics accuse Hollywood of cultural hegemony, the industry can maintain that it only creates content but does not impose ideas and emotions on viewers.

Hollywood has made several attempts to create a universal culture through her films and the global audience have come to rely so much on these films for escapism. The high demand and preference of Hollywood herculean films by the average African is a pointer to the attempt to escape from actual reality. With the increase in insurgency, economic meltdown, and political tussles that birth unemployment and poverty in developing countries, one would only wonder why a people would attempt to escape from the reality by seeking and opting for contents that deviate from the level of realism that portrays actual reality. No wonder the common adage that says “anything that reminds a man of his problem adds to the problem, especially when the resources for the resolution are far from reach. Reflective projective theory explains the tendency of the media to portray conventional values and practice as all serving and self-redeeming. The strength of this theory lies in the ability of the media to present different shades of issues and allow people choose what issues to reflect on in order to meet their needs.

The Distortion of Reality in Hollywood Herculean Films

The core of realism is to creatively capture real life as perfectly, honestly and real as it is. Certain genres of film however, often distort reality, yet appear real –generic verisimilitude. Hollywood herculean films are mostly fantasy fictions and fantasy fiction relies heavily on generic verisimilitude, precisely because so much of its contents center on what is ‘not real’. The regimes of verisimilitude that work in fantasy fiction need to account for these ‘not real’ factors in a manner that provides internal consistency (Culler, 1975). Three Hollywood herculean films have been purposively selected for analyses and these are *Thunder Force*, *Wonder Woman 1984* and *Project Power*. This article looks at how filmmakers utilize certain ‘not real’ factors like tower jumps, flying automobiles, vanishing humans and spectrals, monsters/vampire fights, sun travel, etc. to establish a sense of reality, even when the actual reality is distorted.

Synoptic Discourse of Selected Hollywood Films

Thunder Force is a 2021 super-hero comedy written and directed by Ben Falcone. It revolves

around Lydia Berman (Melissa McCarthy) and Emily Stanton (Octavia Spencer) who set out to put an end to the miscreants' siege in the city of Chicago. The film stretches back to 1983 (when the childhood of Lydia and Emily are portrayed) and into the yet-to-come 2024 (when the anxiety of terminating the miscreants by the duo attains its climax). In March 1983, the Earth was subjected to cosmic rays that brought about the rise of miscreants. With no one able to confront the miscreants, normal people lived in fear of being attacked. Emily's parents are murdered by one of the miscreants and this gets Emily so determined to combat the miscreants, and to avenge her parents' death. Emily sacrifices much of her social life seeking for ways to fight back the miscreants. Lydia supports Emily's dream as her one and only friend but the friendship is strained in 1993 when Lydia accidentally causes Emily to oversleep and wake up late for an exam. By 2024, Emily turns out to be a successful scientist and Lydia, a dockworker. Lydia plans to reconnect with Emily in their high school reunion and invites her to attend. When Emily fails to show up on the night of the reunion, Lydia presumes that Emily is still uncomfortable attending parties by herself and goes to pick her up. Emily tells Lydia that she would have liked to join the reunion but she forgot the date and had a project to work on that night. Lydia inadvertently infuses herself with a serum that Emily had been working on. She learns from Emily that the serum was designed to give a normal person superhuman strength and Emily joins her to take the treatment purposefully, and to take the other super power of invisibility. Upon completion of their training and treatment, Emily and Lydia (having adopted the name 'thunder force') foil a liquor store robbery run by a miscreant with crab arms known as the Crab (Jason Bateman), who falls in love with an equally smitten Lydia, much to Emily's concern. This brings Thunder Force to the attention of mayoral candidate William "The King" Stevens (Bobby Cannavale), who leaves in Chicago at the mercy of the miscreants unless he wins the mayoral election. Thunder Force continues to fight crime with their superpowers and also supports the rival mayoral candidate, thereby causing the King to lose the election. The King then sends Laser (Pom Klementieff) a miscreant who can generate and control whip-like energy beams to attack Thunder Force when they are at a diner. When she tries to get away, Lydia throws a bus at her despite Emily's protests once again straining their friendship. In an effort to make amends, Lydia goes on a date with the Crab where she learns that the King is planning on blowing up everyone who

did not vote for him in the election, even the new mayor, at a disguised party. She tells Emily of what she learned and the duo set out to stop the King from bombing the building. Tracy (Taylor Mosby) - Emily's daughter also joins in the fight having injected herself with her mother's serum. After the fight, Thunder Force realizes that the bomb will go off before they can disarm it; Lydia opts to sacrifice herself to reduce the impact of the explosion by jumping into the Chicago River with it. However, her body is found and resuscitated and with a stronger friendship, they accept the city assistance reward from the Mayor, Rachel Gonzales (Melissa Ponzio).

Wonder woman 1984 is a 2020 film, directed by Patty Jenkins and collaboratively produced by the DC Films, Atlas Entertainment and The Stone Quarry. The film revolves around Diana (Gal Gadot) who is first portrayed as a child in an epic setting on Themyscira, thereafter, as a woman working at the Smithsonian Institution in Washington, D.C while taking up unidentified heroic adventures. Soon, Diana gets entangled in friendship with Barbara Minerva (Kristen Wiig), a new and shy gemologist who works in the museum. After the recovery of some stolen antiquities, the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) calls on the museum to identify the stolen antiquities, here, Diana and Barbara discover an artifact 'dreamstone' that claims to grant one wish of its custodian. The quest to own the dreamstone artefact which is but a deception from Mendecius (the god of lies) pushes Maxwell Lorenzano (Pedro Pascal) to steal it in order to save his oil business from bankruptcy. Without an open declaration of interest for the dream stone, Barbara wishes to possess supernatural powers like Diana, she, who is rather more poised and wishing to reunite with her deceased lover Steve Trevor (Chris Pine) who resurrected in another body; the two are reunited at a Smithsonian party. Diana discovers that the dream stone was created by Mendacius, the god of Lies. It grants a custodian's wish, but exerts a uniformly strong toll lest they renounce the wish or damage the stone. Although Diana's powers and Barbara's humanity begin to diminish, neither of them is willing to renounce their wish. Maxwell visits the U.S President at the White House, who wishes for more nuclear missiles to subdue the Soviets, which brings the world to the edge of nuclear war. Unfortunate for Maxwell, his new found powers soon causes his body to deteriorate and upon his discovery of a satellite system, he decides to exploit this advantage to steal strength and life force from the viewers and regain his health.

Diana and Steve Trevor confront him, but Barbara betrays Diana by knocking her down and escaping with Maxwell on Marine one. Steve Trevor convinces Diana to renounce her wish, this, which she did and consequently regaining her full strength. Upon the recovery, Diana confronts Barbara Minerva and after a brutal fight that ends in a lake, Diana electrocutes Barbara, then pulls her out of the water. She also confronts Maxwell, causing everyone to renounce their wishes against Maxwell's exploitation. She flashes back on Maxwell, a vision of his unhappy childhood and he goes on to denounce his wish as well. Maxwell reunites with his son, Barbara returns back to normal human being after changing to a humanoid and Diana gets to meet the man whose body Steve possessed.

Project Power is a 2020 Super hero film directed by Henry Joost and Ariel Schulman and Written by Mattson Tomlin. The film portrays a pill 'power' that grants various superpowers for five minutes. Outstanding among these illicit pill users is Newt (Colson Baker) who is tracked down by Art (Jamie Foxx) and dies as a result of power overdoses. Art traces Robin Reilly (Dominique Fishback) –Newt's teenage cousin and compels her to take him to the drug baron's safe house. He is shot while exterminating some of the cartel's men, and uncovers that power users in New Orleans are examined as test subjects for the drug. Art connects with Robin and they heal his wounds, and disclose to her that upon leaving the military, he was recruited by Teleios, a secret defense worker who experimented on him to produce superpowers. On the other hand, Frank Shaver (Joseph Gordon-Levitt) - a detective who receives power that hardened his skin, foils a bank robbery by a Power-enhanced thief, but is suspended for using Power himself. His captain divulges that government personnel are compelling him to stop any investigation into Power, and give Frank a picture of the Art, whom they suspect to be the supply of the drug. Frank captures Art and tells his captain, but Art rationalizes that the Power epidemic in New Orleans is mass testing to stabilize the drug, and that Tracy (Kyanna Simone Simpson) - Art's daughter is the source of the drug's powers. Having convinced Frank that his captain is actually taking orders from Teleios, Art purposely has himself captured by Teleios and taken aboard the Genesis. Frank and Robin infiltrate the ship, and Art persuades a guard to free him. Frank and Art kill Wallace (Tait Fletcher) - one who possesses the ability of superhuman strength probably inherited from a rhinoceros, while Robin finds Tracy and reunites her with her

father. As the four attempt to flee, Robin is captured by Dr. Gardner (Amy Landecker) - Wallace's employer, the head of Project Power, who demands Tracy in exchange for Robin's life. Art confronts Gardener but this leads to his death although he is raised back again to life by Tracy and they escape by ship. Frank intends to expose Project Power to the press, while Art decides to move on. He gives Robin his van and a bag of money to pay her mother's medical bills, urging her to make good use of the greatness within her. Art and Tracy are finally free while Robin starts a new career as a rapper.

Intertextuality of the films

The movies under review are selected based on certain shared characteristics. *Thunder Force*, *Wonder Woman 1984* and *Project Power* are all herculean films that try to portray extra ordinary human activities aided by advanced technologies, inventions and power. The selected films also exhibit various actions by the characters that naturally (in reality) would not occur. For instance, in the *Thunder Force*, Lydia throws a bus at Laser as a result of her herculean powers much to Emily's dissatisfaction. In the *Wonder Woman 1984*, Diana flies across the sky as a result of her special and herculean powers as a demigod. In the *Project Power*, Newt is transformed into a flaming figure that gets him fighting with Art superhumanly and unhurt by gun bullets as a result of the power pill. The films portray the ideology that man can be made to act out of the ordinary and from actual reality only by means of a technological or mythical empowerment. In all the films, it is portrayed that herculean activities cannot be done without extreme sophisticated assistance.

Rhetorical Tropes and Modality Critique

Film rhetorical tropes are concerned with the narratives and persuasive elements employed in a film in order to establish believability. Several tropes are used in the selected films to establish the reality portrayed in these films, although, such reality is subsequently infringed and manipulated by some extra ordinary actions that affect total believability as would be considered in this study. Film modality refers to the particular way in which the information on screen is to be encoded or crafted for presentation to the viewers, i.e., to the type of sign and to the status of reality ascribed to or claimed by a sign, text or genre of the film.

In the *Thunder Force*, the narrative first begins by referring to March, 1983, the essence of this is to establish a sense of credibility. Then, a

computer-generated image is used to portray the interstellar cosmic rays upon the Earth, this, which unleashes super-powers on selected few - with this, the actual belief built by the audience for the film as a matter of the date so mentioned is short-lived and truncated as arising from the portrayal of a phenomenon that betrays realism - the cosmic rays' invasion. Again, realism is portrayed in the classroom where the young Emily and Lydia interact with the teacher among other children. The realism established here is sustained through the presentation of buildings and other facilities on the screen that portray an American society while the two keep growing until it is distorted by the introduction of Laser's (miscreant) actions whose rays are computer generated and totally out of true reality. Lydia is seen at the coffee shop where cutleries, seats and tables are shown on screen and here, realism is again established. This turns out to be the longest moments of vivid realism in the film void of unbelievable actions though, until Emily completes her invisibility therapy that gives her the ability to vanish out of sight and at this point, reality is again distorted. Lydia's imaginary love dance with the crab at the mall also adds to the distortion where she spins unbelievably on the air as she dances along. Miscreants' actions (attacks and invasions) in the film are wholly portrayed to be based on rays and lights, such, which are screen generated. The climax of reality distortion here is established when Lydia throws the bus at Laser the miscreant. Tracy's role is distorted towards the end of the film, where she is portrayed to have injected herself with her mother's serum (in order to join in the Gonzales/Chicago defense fight), this which gives her a fictitious racing speed.

In the *Wonder woman 1984*, the narrative first begins by portraying Diana as a child who races across the glades and forest in preparation for the Amazonian contest and then proceeds on to present the contest itself where Diana loses out much to her disappointment. Here, realism is somewhat portrayed until the scene in the city where Diana foils a robbery attempt by using a 'magical' rope that enables her to fly thereby distorting reality. Hence, realism is established again as Diana and Barbara Minerva get along in a cordial relationship. This turns out to be one of the longest moments on the screen where unbelieving actions are excluded from the scenes. The portrayal of the deceased Steve Trevor in the body of a handsome man again betrays realism and this subtle betrayal continues almost to the end of the film where Steve convinces Diana to renounce her wish of having him in order to save her strength from diminishing. Diana's powers as presented in

the film disregards actual reality as obvious in a scene where she outruns the vehicles in a fictitious speed and as well throwing off a truck with a push of her leg. Diana's body resistance to bullets when shot at the White House also distorts reality and her unending surges and flights in the sky without the aid of a visible aircraft adds to this as well.

In the *Project Power*, the narrative first begins with the presentation of a sail and a dock thus giving the impression that the preliminary actions are within a dockyard, where the pill 'power' is introduced. Reality is sustained in the film from its initial scene until Art attacks Newt, which forces the latter to take in the pill in defense of the gunshots. Here, the established screen reality is truncated as Newt is transformed into a flaming being as caused by the pill. Again, realism is distorted in the film when a power-enhanced man with camouflaging and invisibility abilities robs a bank and is shown to be running away from Frank Shaver (a detective) who is also under the effects of the same pill. Realism distortion in the film is sustained in scenes where the pill is being used by or tested on human beings, whose effects on the human body defies medical and biological explanations in reality.

Paradigmatic Analysis

Paradigmatic analysis involves the evaluation of the suggestions embedded in a film and any other work of art. Critically and in regards to this study, it implies weighing such suggestions and comparing them to be in line or not, with reality. Intertextually, the selected films are herculean films whose submissions are but, a projection of supernatural activities which do not portray actual reality. *Thunder Force*, *Wonder Woman 1984* and the *Project Power* all suggest that supernatural problems can only be tackled and combatted through supernatural strategies and skills only. Evident to this in *Thunder Force* is Emily, who devotes all of her time to research for a genetic sequence that can alter the human biochemistry in 'unimaginable' ways in order to stop the miscreants and to avenge her parents' death. This devotion sees to the invention of her serum which Lydia accidentally injects in. Also, in the *Project Power*, 'power' is portrayed as a pill that alters the genetic structure of the human body making one to create chaos or act for a right without being vulnerable to gunshots. Here, Frank Shaver (Joseph Gordon-Levitt) takes in the pill to aid his actions of foiling a bank robbery by a power-enhanced fellow much against the dictates of the government. More so, in the *Wonder Woman 1984*, Diana is portrayed to rely heavily on her herculean abilities during fights and rescues for her ultimate

defense and this adds to the prevailing suggestion that supernatural activities demand herculean abilities to tackle them; this, which do not support actual reality but rather, distorts it.

Summary and Conclusion

Films are largely fictions and seek mainly to entertain viewers but there needs to be a strong connection between what is depicted in the world of film and in the real world, otherwise there would be a dissonance between what is supposed to be and what is in the movie world and the viewers would experience mental discomfort. Realism often helps to bridge the gap, in most instances it attempts to represent real life issues truthfully, without artificiality and avoids speculative fiction and supernatural elements. Hollywood herculean films often defy this order and yet seem realistic –they serve more as avenues for escapism, diverting the attention of viewers from real life (pecuniary) issues that they cannot contend with.

In "*Thunder Force, Wonder Woman 1984 and the Project Power*", it is obvious that some of the scenes as established in the films are set in future or fantasy realms and some scenes are set in our own reality but do not take place on the planet, Earth - this of course distorts the reality embedded in the film. Even with these distortions, film viewers are still susceptible and likely to ask the questions. Realism in film is subjective since people have varied perspectives about what is realistic and what it is not. Realism is therefore defined through the motifs, tropes and the narrative pattern employed in the films – identifying that an adjustment or a drift from the natural will consequently impact on the believability of the films on the part of the viewers.

Hollywood herculean films often defy certain principles of realism and distort reality. While reality can be distorted in many instances to make a film work and to drive in the most desired message, this also can be abused. Realism, as well as everything that can support it, such as sound, deep focus, and undetectable editing, defines what a film should be. Despite the fact that realism gives birth to film as an art form, distortion here definitely implies anything that encourages the production of a feeling or meaning not inherent in the images themselves but derived wholly from their juxtaposition and screen manipulation. Any manipulation of the image, lighting and setting technique stands in the way of releasing film's full potential for reality. Rather than eliminating film as an art form, the introduction of sound enriched it as a necessary component of reality.

This article advocates that things should be presented in their true nature, and dealt with as they are. It opposes any device or technique that is used to alter the audience's view of the scene and its potential for ambiguity and interpretation. The addition of sound, objects, and figures should expose and encode a previously unseen part of reality, enhancing rather than conflicting with the craft of filmmaking. The reality buried in realism should be adequately displayed and not distorted as a result of this. Implicatively, herculean actions in films should be views suspending, interesting and captivating but very unbelieving. To achieve absolute communication and believability in film studies, reality distorted actions in film should be substituted for actions that apply to actual reality in order to address the arising issues in the society.

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